

Assessment of Chemical Properties of Soil in Agricultural Research Land of Abdullahi Fodiyo University of Science And Technology, Aliero, Kebbi State, Nigeria

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Submission: 24th October., 2025; **Accepted:** 17th November, 2025; **Published:** 30th November, 2025

Abstract

The study assessed and analyzed the soils of Abdullahi Fodiyo University of Science and Technology Teaching and Research Farm, Aliero, Kebbi State, Nigeria. The study considered; soil chemical properties, map and analyze the soils of the Study Area. A preliminary survey was initiated to familiarize and select sampling locations, followed by grid survey on 50ha land at a scale of 1:25,000. Land gridding at 100m x 100m intervals apart was undertaken. Baseline was established, followed by augering along intersects for surface sampling of soils to determine boundaries based on differences in soil properties. In each soil mapping unit identified, soil profile pit was dug, described, soil sample collected and labeled from genetic horizon, from bottom up to minimize falling debris contaminants, for laboratory analysis. Each profile pit was dug to standard size; 150cm length, 100cm width and 200cm depth. The description was in accordance with international guidelines. Data set of measured parameters were subjected to descriptive statistics using mean, range and percentages. Three mapping units were identified and labeled ARF1, ARF2 and ARF3. Result from laboratory analysis revealed that soils fertility was low as indicated by low values of 0.09gkg⁻¹, 1.26%, 0.73% 6.70mgkg⁻¹ and 1.46cmolkg⁻¹ representing TN, OM, OC, AP, and CEC respectively. The soils were slightly sodic and non-saline based on ESP and EC ratings. Data on soil chemical properties, would enable understanding, fertility and potential uses of soil, while assisting stakeholders, researchers, farmer and extension agents to properly manage soils of the study area.

Keywords: Baseline, grid, horizon, intersects, profile, Sodicity

1.0 Introduction

Globally, agriculture becomes the largest industry supplying food and providing economic opportunity to the growing human population. Large portion of terrestrial ecosystems across the world are being used for intensive agriculture activities, with a significant human populations engaged in one form of agriculture or the other FAO [1]. The sustainability of productive agricultural land for crop cultivation and its

capacity for food supply relies on soil fertility. Understanding the soil chemical parameters will enhance the sustainable food productivity and agricultural economy. Similarly, Nigeria consist of community of farmers, with large agricultural land mass, though rising peasantry that leads to poverty, food insecurity, hunger and starvation FAO, [1]; as well, low human capital development among others Usman, [2]. Understanding the nature and properties of the soils will enhance good systematic approach and management

practices that will benefit the immediate farming communities of the study area, knowledge seekers and the entire people of Kebbi State.

Farming as well is the main economic activities of the people of Kebbi State, with vast landmass occupied by food crop productions and animal graze-land Usman [2]. in-spites human insecurity by farmers-herders clashes, banditry, and cattle rustling among others. Interest is drawn and focuses on actual composition of the soils of Kebbi State and Aliero. Aliero is found within the tropical Sudan Savannah agroecological zone, consist of its peculiar climatic and ecological features, which majorly influences the composition and characteristics of its soils. Usman [2]. Hou et al [3] suggest that the role of climate, vegetation, and topography in this region leads to specific soil properties. These features emphasized the significance of further detail understanding of the soil chemistry. Hou *et al.*, [3] suggest careful and detailed examination of the physical, chemical, and biological attributes of the soil, which forms the basis of comprehensive understanding of soil composition and behavior. This idea is necessary for farmers, researchers, and land managers, in guiding decisions related to land use, crop selection, and appropriate agricultural interventions. This study builds up the existing literature and provides spring board for specific soil inventory in the study area. Specifically, the study can assists decisions making and predict future land use, management and conservation practices; foster food sufficiency, economic well-being and agricultural sustainability of the study area.

Whereas, expanding human population is exerting pressure on the existing limited productive land resources of the study area. However, the expected population size depends greatly on the availability of land resources and to a reasonable extent, on the availability of friendly environment. Conservation of resource depend on sustainable use of resources, with the sole target of satisfying the societal wants without unnecessary damage to the resource base Kumar *et al.*, [4]. The need for justified and necessary data on the prevalence and composition of soil, types, and extent becomes crucial. Thus, the study of the soils of Aliero area of Kebbi State align in the right place for use in many future aspects of Agricultural and Sustainable economic development.

This study aim to assess and analyze the chemical properties of soils in agricultural research land of Abdullahi Fodiyo University of Science and Technology, Aliero, Kebbi State, Nigeria and to map the soil of the study area.

2.0 Materials and Method

2.1 The Study Area

The study was carried out in the Abdullahi Fodiyo University of Science and Technology Teaching and Research Farm, Aliero, Kebbi State, Nigeria. It is located on Latitude 12°18'.938N and Longitude 4°9'33.504E. It has a total area of 412km² and is bordered in the East by Tambuwal Local Government Area of Sokoto State, in the Northwest by Birnin Kebbi Local Government Area, in the Southwest by Jega Local Government Area Ambursa *et al.*, [5], KARDa [6].

The population of Kebbi State is estimated about 3,630,931 people NPCN-KB, [7]. The vegetation type of Aliero is climatically defined into Sudan Savanna vegetation (Semi – arid zone of the country). The vegetation is characterized by dense population of grasses with scanty shrubs and few trees (coexistence of trees and grasses), high rainfall variability and high temperature. Natural vegetation in Aliero is characterized by open woodland with scattered trees such as *Pakia biglobosa*, *Vitellaria paradoxa*, *Combretum species* and Dum palms etc (Ambursa *et al.* [5].

The zone is mostly affected by frequent droughts and desertification, poor soil fertility; as well as incidence of flooding as a result of climate change, with attendant intense pressure of anthropogenic activities and climate change. The vegetation cover is gradually becoming degraded. Some part of this study are has extended to Sahel due to desertification, posing more threat to endangered species and accelerating the extinction of certain tree species of higher economic importance. It also accelerates biodiversity loss, soil organic matter degradation and stability of soil structure as well as soil biota. These further changes the environmental conditions and the climate Bello, [8]; Adamu, [9].

Massive flood plains of in-land river valley system dominates the study area, with overflow from Sabiyel Lake and Tagangu seasonal rivers. Aliero

has a flat but undulating elevation of about 150m in the flood plains, with an alluvial sediments ranges from gravel to clay. The sediment gets saturated during the rains to store water in the sands for dry season use. The geology of Aliero is characterized by thick sedimentary deposit of the Sokoto-Rima basin. It is also under laid by Precambrian Basement Rocks in Singh, as sited by Ambursa *et al.* [5].

Aliero is a tropical type climate generally characterized by wet and dry season. The rainfall begins April with the heaviest rainfall recorded in July and August KARDA [6]. The cold harmattan periods that come with dust laden wind prevails in the month of November to February, while the months of March to May are extremely hot KARDA op sit. The mean annual temperature varies considerably but usually stands at 42^oC. The mean annual rainfall is 500mm Ambursa [5]. Relative humidity range is 21-47% and 57-59% during the dry and rainy seasons respectively.

Soil type and fertility vary from place to place, ranging from loamy sand, sandy clay and to a large extent sandy loam KARDA, [6]. The crops commonly grown in the area include cereal crops, such as maize, guinea corn, millet, common

vegetable like tomatoes, pepper, lettuce, spinach, Roots crops like onions, while tuber crops such as potatoes and cassava are grown. Tree crops include Mangoes, Cashew and Guava, KADP, [10]. The soils of Kebbi State are mostly Entisols Usman, [11] and Aridisols, Soil Survey Staff [12]. They are highly weathered and fragile with low activity clays, thus making their fertility decline under continuous arable cropping IUSS, [13]. As Aridisols, they are characterized as slowly permeable with most of the water lost by run-off. They might have been formed under aridity from wind-stored desert sands that accumulated over a long period of time.

In addition, some soils in Aliero have also been attributed to ferruginous tropic soil D'Hoore, [14] and characterized as having sandy texture, covering a large area of land with very low water holding capacity and low organic matter, Nitrogen, Phosphorus content, neutral or moderately acidic in pH and also having low cation exchange capacity (CEC). The vegetation in the desert or semi desert area is usually sparse and the surface is bare for long period of time. This may contribute to soil degradation by wind erosion and hence, cause soil fertility to decline in the area,

Figure 1: Maps of Kebbi State (Left) and Aliero (Right) Extracted from Map of Nigeria (Top Right)

Source: Kebbi State Geographic Information System (KSGIS)

2.2 Research Design

The researcher first embarked on a reconnaissance survey of the study area. An intensive grid survey with Land gridding at 100m x 100m intervals apart was undertaken using square method. Baseline was established, followed by augering along intersects for surface sampling of soils to determine boundaries based on differences in soil properties, was conducted in the Abdullahi Fodiyo University of Science and Technology Teaching and Research Farm (ARF), Aliero on a mapping scale of 1:25,000 covering a 500,000m² (50 ha) land. To establish soil surface sampling point in the study area, points were mapped out with visible pegs and coordinates taken on the 50ha land as illustrated in the figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Surface Sampling Points of the Study Area

2.3 Sampling Technique

Surface and subsurface soils were collected at a depth of 0-15cm and 15-30cm using soil auger and stainless steel scoop in line with the procedure described by FAO [1] guideline.

2.4 Soil Profile Description

Each soil mapping unit identified in the study area had a profile pit dug and described. Soil samples from each horizon were collected using stainless

scoop from bottom up the profile to minimize contamination by falling debris, for laboratory analysis. Each profile pit was dug to 150cm length, 100cm wide and 200cm depth. Description of each profile pit was done according to FAO, [1]; and soil survey staff, [12] guidelines. Soil depth, horizon thickness, colour of matrix and mottles, texture, structure, consistency, porosity, inclusive materials, roots and horizon boundary were determined and described for each horizon of the pedons, Soil Survey Staff [12]. Fig.3 show soil mapping units of the study area.

Figure 3: Soil Mapping Unit

2.5 Laboratory Analysis

Organic Carbon (OC)

Soil organic carbon was determined using the 1934 Wet Oxidation Method of Walkley-Black sited by Nelson and Summar [15]. The method involved digesting the soil sample with a mixture of conc. acid-dicromate ($K_2Cr_2O_7H_2SO_4$ and H_2PO_4) and adding phenyl amine indicator. The excess $K_2Cr_2O_7$ was then titrated with $FeSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ solution (1N).

Total Nitrogen (TN)

Total Nitrogen was determined by Micro Kjeldahl digestion and distillation method as described by Jackson [16]. The method involved digesting 2g of soil sample in concentrated H_2SO_4 and heating in a

block digester at very high temperature (400⁰C), broth turn clear. The clear mixture was diluted with water and 40% NaOH was added to the mixture and the mixture distilled in Micro-Kjeldahl apparatus and received in boric acid. This was then titrated with 0.1m HCl (Jackson *et al.*, [17]).

Available Phosphorus (P)

Available Phosphorus was extracted using Bray-1 method (0.025M HCl + 0.03M NH₄F) as described by Bray and Kutz [18]. Available Phosphorus in the extract was determined colorimetrically using blue ammonium molybdate ascorbic acid method.

Soi pH

Soil pH was determined using glass electrode digital pH meter in a 1:2 soil water mixture as recommended by 1988 Alberta Provincial Laboratory.

Exchangeable Basic Cations (EBC)

Exchangeable Basic Cations (Ca, Mg, K and Na) in the soil were extracted with 1.0M ammonium acetate (NH₄OAc) extracting solution buffered at pH7. Exchangeable Ca and Mg was determined by 1974 EDTA titration method as described by Steward. Flame photometry method, Uriyo and Singh [19] was used to determine Exchangeable K and Na concentration in solution.

Cation Exchange Capacity (CEC)

Soil CEC was determined by ammonium saturation method of 1965 as described by Chapman. The soil will be saturated with excess neutral NH₄OAc solution and washing with excess alcohol.

Electrical Conductivity (EC)

Electrical Conductivity meter was used to determine the electrical conductivity in a 1:2 soil water ratio at 25⁰C. The result was multiplied by a conversion factor of 2.063 as suggested by Alberta Provincial Laboratory in 1988 to obtain the saturation extract.

2.6 Data Analysis

The data on soil chemical properties was subjected to descriptive statistics where means, ranges and percentages obtained were used to compare the differences that exist within the study area.

Exchangeable Sodium Percentage (ESP)

This can be expressed as

$$ESP = \frac{Na}{CEC} \times 100$$

ESP Surface Soil = 14.86%, ESP ARF1 = 15.00%, ESP ARF2 = 12.90%, ESP ARF3 = 14.97%

Ratings of ESP

<5%: Normal (Non sodic), 5-15%: Slightly sodic and >15: Sodic, Abdulahi and Ibrahim [20].

Sodium Adsorption Ration (SAR)

This can be expressed as

$$SAR = \frac{Na}{\sqrt{\frac{Ca+Mg}{2}}}$$

SAR Surface Soil = 0.39, SAR ARF1 = 0.40, SAR ARF2 = 0.91, SAR ARF3 = 0.15

Ratings SAR

<13-Non-Sodic, >13-Sodic, 13-Slightly Sodic and >25-Highly Sodic (Abdulahi and Ibrahim, [44])

3.0 Result and Discussion

The chemical properties of soils of the mapping units are presented in tables and figures.

3.1 Chemical Properties of the Surface Soils

The chemical properties of the surface soils are presented in Table 1. This includes soil pH, Electrical Conductivity (EC), Organic Matter (OM), Organic Carbon (OC), Total Nitrogen (TN), Available Phosphorus (AP), Basic Cations (Ca, Mg, K, and Na) and Cation Exchange Capacity (CEC).

The pH for surface soils ranged from a minimum of 3.6 to a maximum of 6.8 approximately, with an overall mean value of 5.05 (Fig.4). The mean value of pH (5.1) for surface soil indicates strongly acidic condition using the USDA-NRCS [36], rating scale.

This might influence nutrient availability and microbial activities, and finally affecting the overall soil health. The study therefore, contradicts the results of El Tahir et al. [22] and KADP [26],

Moss, [23], who reported that soil pH for Sudan Savannah Soil range from 6.5-7.5 (slightly acidic to neutral) and 6.0-7.3 (moderately acidic to neutral) for some Kebbi State Soils.

Soil management practices that can neutralize the acidic condition of this study are become necessary through organic amendments and liming. Also rate of fertilizer applications should be based on soil test.

Table 1: Chemical Properties of the Surface Soils at 0 – 30 cm

Sample ID	pH	EC (dsm ⁻¹)	OC (%)	TN (gkg ⁻¹)	AP (Mgkg ⁻¹)	Ca	Mg	K	Na	CEC (Cmolkg ⁻¹)
						(cmolkg ⁻¹)				
P1	6.78	0.0305	0.95	0.06	6.20	0.07	0.80	0.05	0.07	0.99
P2	5.63	0.0217	0.59	0.06	6.33	0.07	0.81	0.04	0.07	0.99
P3	5.63	0.0196	0.88	0.06	5.00	0.05	1.01	0.03	0.06	1.20
P4	5.56	0.0281	0.29	0.06	5.50	0.11	0.30	0.03	0.07	0.51
P5	5.90	0.0196	0.01	0.06	6.50	0.09	0.24	0.04	0.07	0.44
P6	5.68	0.0196	0.29	0.05	6.50	0.07	0.30	0.05	0.10	0.52
P7	5.19	0.0266	0.59	0.07	6.63	0.10	0.80	0.04	0.09	1.03
P8	5.27	0.0274	0.59	0.06	6.50	0.18	0.80	0.07	0.05	1.10
P9	3.60	0.0289	0.01	0.04	4.50	0.13	0.21	0.06	0.13	0.53
P10	5.10	0.0233	2.11	0.08	8.21	0.11	2.50	0.04	0.08	2.73
P11	3.89	0.0283	0.59	0.07	8.20	0.14	0.79	0.09	0.11	1.13
P12	5.33	0.0186	1.19	0.07	7.50	0.13	1.97	0.06	0.11	2.27
P13	5.59	0.0528	0.59	0.06	4.30	0.30	0.81	0.05	0.25	1.41
P14	4.54	0.0192	0.29	0.07	6.15	0.14	0.31	0.03	0.13	0.61
P15	5.49	0.0140	0.88	0.06	6.22	0.07	1.00	0.05	0.15	1.27
P16	4.66	0.0198	0.59	0.07	6.33	0.16	0.82	0.04	0.16	1.18
P17	4.57	0.0264	0.88	0.06	5.20	0.24	1.02	0.20	1.41	2.87
P18	5.09	0.0413	1.19	0.05	5.20	0.36	1.96	0.12	0.15	2.59
P19	5.19	0.0268	0.59	0.05	5.00	0.15	0.80	0.04	0.19	1.18
P20	4.41	0.0365	0.59	0.06	5.00	0.07	0.82	0.16	0.83	1.93
P21	5.55	0.0274	0.29	0.07	6.00	0.12	0.31	0.15	1.24	1.82
P22	4.76	0.0264	0.59	0.05	6.01	0.12	0.78	0.16	1.25	2.31
P23	4.44	0.0264	2.74	0.09	8.50	0.07	3.50	0.11	0.88	4.56
P24	5.02	0.0301	0.88	0.08	8.55	0.34	1.00	0.09	0.88	2.31
P25	4.84	0.0367	1.49	0.06	6.10	0.33	2.30	0.09	0.82	3.54
P26	4.37	0.0258	0.29	0.05	5.86	0.03	0.29	0.06	0.74	1.12
P27	4.87	0.0264	0.88	0.06	5.50	0.19	1.02	0.21	0.35	1.77
P28	5.21	0.0235	0.59	0.06	5.00	0.15	0.81	0.03	0.13	1.12
P29	4.72	0.0243	0.59	0.05	5.00	0.13	0.76	0.04	0.17	1.10
P30	5.35	0.0252	0.59	0.08	8.20	0.23	0.78	0.07	0.18	1.26
P31	4.98	0.0289	0.88	0.09	8.50	0.18	1.01	0.06	0.18	1.43
P33	5.03	0.0243	0.88	0.09	8.25	0.14	1.01	0.03	0.16	1.34
P34	4.64	0.0301	0.88	0.05	5.00	0.11	1.01	0.03	0.17	1.32
P35	5.26	0.0223	0.88	0.05	5.25	0.02	1.02	0.05	0.16	1.25
P36	4.32	0.0246	0.59	0.09	5.80	0.14	0.80	0.04	0.15	1.13
P37	4.62	0.0398	1.19	0.07	8.21	0.23	1.95	0.05	0.15	2.38
P38	5.24	0.0256	0.88	0.09	8.50	0.02	1.00	0.03	0.18	1.23
P39	4.69	0.0281	1.19	0.09	8.10	0.12	1.95	0.04	0.12	2.23
P40	5.29	0.0324	0.29	0.06	5.00	0.12	0.29	0.03	0.13	0.57
P41	4.86	0.0219	0.59	0.06	5.12	0.11	0.79	0.04	0.13	1.07
P43	5.23	0.0279	0.29	0.09	8.56	0.16	0.30	0.04	0.13	0.63
P45	5.16	0.0221	0.59	0.09	8.78	0.18	0.81	0.04	0.18	1.21

Sample ID	pH	EC (dSm ⁻¹)	OC (%)	TN (gkg ⁻¹)	AP (Mgkg ⁻¹)					CEC (Cmolkg ⁻¹)
						Ca	Mg	K	Na	
P46	5.02	0.0336	0.29	0.09	8.50	0.14	0.31	0.04	0.17	0.66
P47	4.38	0.0219	0.59	0.08	8.21	0.08	0.81	0.03	0.17	1.09
P48	5.07	0.0239	0.88	0.09	8.56	0.02	1.01	0.05	0.23	1.13
P49	5.33	0.0213	1.49	0.08	8.20	0.23	2.30	0.08	0.29	2.90
P50	5.42	0.0169	0.29	0.06	6.00	0.27	2.29	0.03	0.18	0.77
P52	5.32	0.0206	0.59	0.08	8.20	0.19	0.80	0.05	0.16	1.20
P53	4.78	0.0293	0.88	0.09	8.50	0.05	1.02	0.06	0.17	1.30
P54	5.71	0.0243	0.29	0.06	5.50	0.12	0.30	0.03	0.13	0.58
Mean	5.05	0.0265	0.73	0.09	6.70	0.14	0.95	0.06	0.29	1.46

KEY: pH = Acidity or alkality, EC = Electrical Conductivity, OC = Organic Carbon, TN = Total Nitrogen, AP = Available Phosphorus, Ca = Calcium, Mg = Magnesium, K = Potassium, Na = Sodium, CEC = Cation Exchange Capacity

Figure 4: Soil pH Map

Electrical Conductivity (EC) for the surface soils range from a minimum of 0.014–a maximum of 0.053dSm⁻¹, with overall mean value of 0.0265 dSm⁻¹.

Smith and Doran, [24] categorized soil salinity as 0-1.4dSm⁻¹ (non-saline, 1.2-2.8dSm⁻¹(slightly saline), 2.5-2.7dSm⁻¹(moderately saline), 4.5-11.4dSm⁻¹(strongly saline) and 9.0-11.5dSm⁻¹ very strongly saline. However, Tahir [25], reported that soil EC values of <2dSm⁻¹ indicates low salinity (suitable for crops development), 2-4dSm⁻¹ moderate salinity (may require special management practices for sensitive crops), 4-8dSm⁻¹ high salinity (may require drainage or other remediation measures to support plant growth) and >8dSm⁻¹ indicates extremely high salinity (may not be suitable for most crops).

Therefore, the mean value of EC at 0.027dSm⁻¹ for surface soils was rated low and non-saline.

The results for the Organic Matter (OM) ranged from 0.02-4.71% and a mean value of 1.26%, highest value (4.71%) and lowest (0.02%). Organic Matter (OM) rating by Tahir [25] shows that OM>20% is very high, 10-20% high, 4-10% medium, 2-4% low and <2% very low. Therefore, the available OM (1.26%) recorded in this study is very low,

which could be attributed to continuous crops cultivation without sustainable agricultural practices. Additionally, incessant bush burning as a cheap means of clearing for farming operations, burning of farm residues (pre and post-harvest) further destroy OM and decomposer micro-organisms. The extent of plants life and density is also a contributory factor to OM level. The low OM reported in this study, is supported by previous research conducted by Syauswa [26], which revealed low OM as a critical aspect of soils in Sudan Savannah. Organic soil amendment and crop rotation is important to address soil fertility degradation. Organic Carbon (OC) as a function of Organic Matter (OM), assumed a similar level of occurrence and distribution pattern from the surface soils and subsurface horizons of the soil profiles (Fig.5). This is because they are interwoven as basic essential components of soil fertility assessment. From Table 1, OC for surface soils ranged from a minimum of 0.29 to a maximum of 2.74% with an overall mean value of 0.73%. The highest is 12.74%, and the lowest is 0.29%.

In terms of spread, OC reflects OM for surface soils. According to Esu [27], OC< 1.0% is

categorized as low, 1.0- 1.5% medium, and > 1.5% high for savannah soils. Therefore, the mean value of 0.73% OC for surface soils is considered low.

Figure 5: Soil Organic Carbon Map

In the surface soils, Total Nitrogen (TN) had a range of 0.04-0.09gkg⁻¹ with an overall mean value of 0.09gkg⁻¹ (Fig.6 and Fig.7). According the TN rating by Esu, [27, 28], <0.1gkg⁻¹ indicate low TN, 0.1-0.2gkg⁻¹ medium, and >0.2gkg⁻¹ high. Therefore, the mean value of 0.09gkg⁻¹ TN for surface soils represents low concentration, which could be due to leaching, land use, or erosion by runoff, Abdullahi and Ibrahim [20]

Figure 6; Soil Interpolated Total Nitrogen Map

Figure 7: Soil Normalized Total Nitrogen Map

Available phosphorus (AP) for the surface soils had a range of 4.30-8.78mgkg⁻¹ and a mean value of 6.70mgkg⁻¹. Ratings of AP by Esu, [27, 28], is given as <10mgkg⁻¹ low, 10-20mgkg⁻¹ moderate and >20mgkg⁻¹ high. This signifies that the surface soils mean AP value of 6.70mgkg⁻¹ is considered low.

Figure 8: Soil Interpolated Available Phosphorus Map

Figure 9: Soil Normalized Available Phosphorus Map

Exchangeable Bases (basic cations) such as Ca, Mg, K and Na for surface soils were presented in Table 1. The surface soils Ca recorded a range of 0.02 - 0.36cmolk⁻¹ and a mean value of 0.14cmolk⁻¹. By the ratings of Esu, [27], < 2cmolk⁻¹ indicate low Ca medium and >5cmolk⁻¹ high. Therefore, the mean value of 0.14cmolk⁻¹ Ca recorded for surface soils represent low status.

Figure 11: Soil Normalized Ca Map

Exchangeable Mg for the surface soils shows a range 0.21-3.50 cmolk⁻¹ Mg, with a mean value of 0.95 cmolk⁻¹. By Esu, [28] ratings < 0.3 cmolk⁻¹ Mg indicates low and >1.0 cmolk⁻¹ high, the mean value of 0.95 cmolk⁻¹ Mg is rated a moderate level.

Figure 10: Soil Interpolated Available Calcium Map

Figure 12: Soil Interpolated Magnesium Map

Figure 13: Soil Normalize Magnesium Map

Exchangeable K for surface soil recorded a range of $0.03 - 0.21 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$ and a mean value of 0.06 cmolkg^{-1} K (Fig.14 and 15). Ratings show that $>0.15 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$ signifies low, $0.15-0.3 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$ medium and $>0.3 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$ high. Therefore, the mean value of 0.06 cmolkg^{-1} K for surface soils indicates low status.

Figure 14: Soil Interpolated Potassium Map

Figure 15: Soil Normalize Potassium Map

Exchangeable Na for surface soils was seen within the range of $0.05-1.41 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$, with the highest of 1.41 cmolkg^{-1} and lowest being 0.05 cmolkg^{-1} . The mean value was 0.29 cmolkg^{-1} . From the ratings of Na $<0.1 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$ indicates low, $0.1-0.3$ moderate, and $>0.3 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$ high. This means that, the mean value of 0.29 cmolkg^{-1} Na for surface soils is considered moderate.

From the results of Exchangeable bases for surface soils, it shows that Exchangeable Mg dominated other basic cations with a leading 0.95 cmolkg^{-1} , followed by Na with 0.29 cmolkg^{-1} . General knowledge in Tropical Sudan Savannah studies indicate that soils tend to have moderate to high levels of exchangeable bases, but variable status of exchangeable bases abound in some areas, particularly for Ca and Mg. This therefore highlights comprehending the complexities of factors such as parent material, geological processes, soil type, pH, particle size, land use, topography, Organic Matter (OM), that affect exchangeable bases availability. For instance, granitic parent materials tend to produce higher sand fractions which can impact Ca levels. This is evident in the surface soils of the study area where Sand fraction was dominant, thereby resulting in low Ca level. Also, Nitrogenous fertilizers can lower pH and accelerate acidity in soils, thereby potentially influencing Ca availability.

From Table 1, Cation Exchange Capacity (CEC) expression of the surface soils ranged from 0.44 - 4.56, with a mean value of 1.46 cmolkg^{-1} (Fig.16 and 17). By Esu, [28] rating, $\text{CEC} < 6 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$ is low, 6-12 medium, and $>12 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$ high. The mean value recorded for CEC as 1.46 cmolkg^{-1} is considered low. The low CEC could be due to strong acidic pH status of 5.1, low OM content as well as granitic sand dominance of the surface soils IUSS, [13]. The overall fertility of the study area is shown in Fig.18 and Fig.19.

Figure 16 Soil Interpolated CEC Map

Figure 17: Soil Normalise CEC Map

Figure 18: Soil Fertility margin Map

Figure 19: Soil Fertility level Map

Table 2: Chemical Properties of the Soil Profiles

Pedon (200cm)	Horizon	Depth (cm)	pH	EC (dsm ⁻¹)	OM (%)	OC (%)	TN (gkg ⁻¹)	AP (Mgkg ⁻¹)	Ca	Mg	K	Na	CEC
SOIL UNIT ARF1 Lat. 12^o.31528N, Long. 4^o.50583E, Alt:246.2m													
1	Ap	0-10	4.92	0.0217	1.01	0.59	0.07	20.00	0.00	0.35	0.04	0.13	0.52
	Ah	10-21	5.47	0.0175	1.52	0.88	0.06	23.50	0.00	1.00	0.05	0.23	1.28
	Btg	21-101	4.42	0.0089	0.50	0.29	0.06	6.30	0.10	1.50	0.07	0.40	2.07
	Bcg	101-182	4.22	0.0091	1.01	0.59	0.11	6.33	0.10	1.50	0.10	0.44	2.14
	Mean		4.76	0.0143	1.01	0.59	0.08	14.03	0.05	1.09	0.07	0.30	1.50
SOIL UNIT ARF2 Lat. 12^o.31389N, Long. 4^o.50583E, Alt:264m													
2	Ap	0-11	4.76	0.0398	3.09	1.80	0.09	25.50	0.10	0.38	0.05	0.19	0.72
	AB	11-32	4.35	0.0365	2.56	1.49	0.08	20.00	0.07	1.50	0.05	0.22	1.84
	Btg	32-122	4.33	0.0322	3.09	1.80	0.06	9.90	0.10	1.50	0.06	0.18	1.84
	C	121.-192	4.24	0.0186	2.04	1.19	0.10	10.50	0.00	1.55	0.05	0.20	1.80
	Mean		4.42	0.0318	2.70	1.57	0.08	16.48	0.07	1.23	0.05	0.20	1.55
SOIL UNIT ARF3 Lat. 12^o.31056N, Long. 4^o.49611E, Alt:267m													
3	Ap	0-11	4.85	0.0169	1.01	0.59	0.08	20.50	0.10	1.20	0.05	0.21	1.56
	AB	11-41	4.91	0.0303	1.01	0.59	0.07	20.00	0.07	1.50	0.04	0.38	1.99
	Bc	41-112	4.88	0.0246	1.01	0.59	0.06	9.00	0.03	1.00	0.04	0.19	1.26
	Bt	112-190	4.27	0.0213	1.52	0.88	0.11	10.45	0.10	1.50	0.04	0.23	1.87
	Mean		4.73	0.0233	1.14	0.66	0.08	14.93	0.08	1.30	0.04	0.25	1.67

KEY: pH = Acidity or alkality, EC = Electrical Conductivity, OM = Organic matter, OC = Organic Carbon, TN = Total Nitrogen, AP = Available Phosphorus, Ca = Calcium, Mg = Magnesium, K = Potassium, Na = Sodium, CEC = Cation Exchange Capacity

Source: Author's Field and Laboratory soil Analysis

3.2 Chemical Properties of the Soil Profiles

The chemical properties of soils of the mapping unit profiles are presented in Table 2. They include pH, Electrical Conductivity (EC), Organic Matter (OM), Organic Carbon (OC), Total Nitrogen (TN), Available Phosphorus (AP), Basic Cations (Ca, Mg, K, and Na) and Cation Exchange Capacity (CEC).

pH for the surface and subsurface horizons of soil in unit ARF1 shows a range of 4.2-5.5 and a mean value of 4.8. The surface horizons had a range of 4.9-5.5 and subsurface horizon had a range of 4.2-4.4. Irregular distribution of pH with depth was

observed. By rating, the mean value of 4.8 indicates very strong acidic soil.

Soil unit ARF2 surface and subsurface horizons had a pH range of a minimum of 4.2 in C horizon to 4.8 in AP horizon and a mean value of 4.4. Surface horizon range from 4.4-4.8 and subsurface horizons ranged from 4.2-4.3. A regular decrease in pH with depth was observed. The mean value of 4.4pH indicates extremely acidic condition.

In soil unit ARF3, the surface and subsurface horizons recorded a mean value of 4.7 pH at a range of 4.3 in Bt horizon-4.9 in AP horizon. An irregular trend of increase and decrease in pH with depth of profile was observed. The mean value of 4.7 pH indicates very strongly acid condition.

An overview of the pH results from the surface soils to the surface and subsurface horizons of the three mapping units ARF1, ARF2 and ARF3 with mean values as 5.1, 4.8, 4.4 and 4.7 respectively, indicates acidic conditions. This may impact the nutrient supply and microbial activities, affecting the overall soil health of the study area. The study therefore, contradicts with the results from studies conducted by El Tahir, [8] and KADP [10], Moss, [22], which stated that soil pH for Sudan Savannah range from 6.5-7.5 (slightly acidic to neutral) and 6.0-7.3 (moderately acidic to neutral) for some Kebbi State Soils.

However, the study aligned with El-Tahir, [40] on the assumption that variation in pH depends on soil depth, texture and land use practices. Observably, from the surface soils down to the surface and subsurface horizons of the profile, there seen to be a decrease in pH values with depth. On the basis of texture, the Sand (S), Loamy Sand (LS) and Sandy Clay Loam were seen to record higher values of pH. For land use practices, the acidic condition of the entire study area could be attributed to the constant application of chemical fertilizers (NPK, Urea, Murate of Potash), herbicides and pesticides, which percolate down the soils over time to form various chemical bonding of acidic nature. Again, in my view, variation in pH down the profile may be hinged on the selective interplay between the soil solution and soil complex (exchange sites), based on ions affinity, selective adsorption and isomorphous substitution in the tetrahedral and octahedral lattices of the soil complex.

For the study area to favour agricultural productivity (crop growth and yield), management practices that can reduce the acidic condition to slightly or neutral pH becomes necessary. Such include: organic amendments, liming, reduced use of pesticide and herbicides (but if necessary to apply, must be supervised by an expert as agronomist, Crop Scientist, Plant Pathologist or Entomologist). Also rate of fertilizer applications should be based on soil test and recommendations.

EC for surface and subsurface horizons of soil unit ARF1 had a range of 0.0089 to 0.0217 dsm^{-1} and a mean value of 0.0143 dsm^{-1} . The highest value of 0.0217 dsm^{-1} was located at AP horizon, while the lowest (0.0089 dsm^{-1}) locates at Btg horizons. The surface horizon had a range of 0.0175-0.0217 dsm^{-1}

and the subsurface range from 0.0089-0.0091 dsm^{-1} . A regular decrease in EC with depth up to Btg horizon was observed.

Soil unit ARF2 surface and subsurface horizons had a range of 0.0816-0.0398 dsm^{-1} and a mean value of 0.0318 dsm^{-1} . The highest (0.0398 dsm^{-1}) occurred at the Ap, while the lowest (0.0186 dsm^{-1}) occurred at the C horizon. The surface horizons range from 0.0365-0.0398 dsm^{-1} and the subsurface had a range of 0.0186-0.0322 dsm^{-1} . A decrease in EC with depth was observed throughout the Pedon.

Soil unit ARF3 has a surface and subsurface range of 0.0169-0.0303 dsm^{-1} and a mean value of 0.0233 dsm^{-1} . The highest (0.0303 dsm^{-1}) was found at Ap horizon, while the lowest (0.0169 dsm^{-1}) was sited at the Ap horizon. The surface horizons recorded a range of 0.0169-0.0303 dsm^{-1} and the subsurface got a range of 0.0213-0.0246 dsm^{-1} . By ratings, the mean values of ARF1 (0.0143 dsm^{-1}), ARF2 (0.0318 dsm^{-1}) and ARF3 (0.0233 dsm^{-1}) were rated low and consider non-saline. This implies that the entire study area with EC of <2 dsm^{-1} could be suitable for most crops. Furthermore, the low EC in the study area may be attributed to the generally low proportion of clay and silt contents (smaller soil particles), as against the dominance sand fraction, based on the notion by USDA [21], that soils with higher clay content conduct more electrical current than soils with higher silt and sand particles.

However, El Tahir [25] also noted that low EC of <4 dsm^{-1} does not guarantee maximum yield, as it can result in considerable yield loss, perhaps due to problem of fixation.

The soil unit ARF1 surface and subsurface horizons recorded a range of 0.50-1.52% OM, with a mean value of 1.01%. The highest range of 1.52% occurred at the Ah horizon, while the lowest 0.50% situates at Btg horizons. The range for the surface horizons lied between 1.01-1.52% and that of subsurface horizons was between 0.50-1.01%. Irregular trend of increase and decrease with depth of the profile was observed. The mean value of 1.01% is considered very low.

In soil unit ARF2, surface and subsurface horizon recorded a range of 2.04-3.09% OM and a means value of 2.70%. The highest value (3.09%) was

found at the Ap and Btg horizons, while the lowest value (2.04%) occurred at C horizon. The surface horizons range from 2.56-3.09% and the subsurface has as range of 2.04-3.09%. An irregular distribution trend with depth of profile was observed. The mean value of 2.70% was rated low.

Soil unit ARF3 profile with a range of 1.01-1.52% had a mean value of 1.14%. The highest 1.52% occurred at the Bt, while the lowest 1.01% situates at the Ap, AB and BC horizons. Surface horizons range was fixed at 1.01% and subsurface horizons varied from 1.01-1.52%. Increase with depth pattern of distribution was observed and the mean value of 1.14% was rated very low.

By implications, the entire study area exhibits a low OM status. The low OM reported in this study, is supported by previous research conducted by Syauserwa, [41], which revealed low OM as a critical aspect of soils in Sudan Savannah. Further extensive research on physical and chemical properties of soils in Sudan Savannah by Wuaku, [6], Motsi, [7], gave backings to low OM content. D'Hoore, [14], also reported that some soils in Kebbi State are ferruginous with low Organic Matter (OM) etc.

Imperatively, OM being a vital component influencing soil fertility, nutrient availability, microbial activities, aggregate stability, water retention and nutrient cycling, underscores the importance of organic amendments by integrating organic materials into the soils to addressing fertility limitations, structural deficits and mitigate erosion and conservation. Additionally, to enhance OM sustainability, , rotational cover crops with groundnut, cowpea, *Calapogonium mucunoides*, *Centrosema pubescens*, *Pueraria phaseoloides*, among others should be incorporated in between cropping seasons, as some are symbiotic (plant-bacteria relationship) in nature, while some also exhibit a tripartite synergism (plant-fungi-bacteria relationship).

The irregular and regular pattern of OM distribution with depth of the profile recorded in the study could be attributed to plants life and density of spread (vegetation cover), presence and degree of microbial activities, leaching, eluviation, management practices (irrigation) and anthropogenic activities, Wall [29].

Organic Carbon (OC) as a function of Organic Matter (OM), assumed a similar level of occurrence and distribution pattern from the surface soils to the surface and subsurface horizons of the profiles. This is because they are interwoven as basic essential components of soil fertility. According to ratings of OC by Esu, [26], OC<1.0% is low, 1.0-1.5% medium, and >1.5% high for savannah soils.

Soil unit ARF1 had a surface and subsurface horizons range of 0.29-0.88% and a mean value of 0.59%. The highest (0.88%) was seen at the Ah horizon, while the lowest (0.29%) occurred at Btg horizon. The surface horizons recorded a range of 0.59-0.88% and the subsurface horizon took a range of 0.29-0.59%. The mean value of 0.59% OC was rated low.

Soil unit ARF2 recorded a range of 1.19-1.80% for surface and subsurface horizon with a mean value of 1.57%, the highest being 1.80% and the lowest as 1.19%. The highest range occurred at Ap and Btg horizons, while the lowest at C horizon. The range for the surface horizons stood at 1.49-1.80% and that of subsurface horizon is between 1.19-1.80%. The mean value of 1.157% OC was rated at high. This could be attributed to the reasonable (near luxuriant) vegetation cover around the mapping unit, its flood pruned topography and dominant soil type of Sandy Clay Loam (SCL), which make for accumulation of organic materials and decomposition due to favourable micro-climate.

Soil unit ARF3 with a range of 0.59- 0.88%, took a mean value of 0.66% OC for surface and subsurface horizons. The highest range of 0.88% occurred at the Bt horizon, while the lowest range (0.59%) took position at Ap, AB and BC horizons. The surface horizons recorded a steady range of 0.59% and the subsurface horizons range from 0.59-0.88. The mean value of 0.66% OC by ratings of Esu, [28] was considered low.

In view of the foregoing records of OC and OM in the study, it can be predicted that soil unit ARF2 has potential soil fertility status with sustainable agricultural strategies put in place.

Soil unit ARF1 had a range of 0.06-0.11gkg⁻¹ and a mean value of 0.08gkg⁻¹ TN. The highest value (0.11gkg⁻¹) occurred at the BCg horizon, while the

lowest value (0.06gkg^{-1}) pitched at Ah and Btg horizons, the surface horizon had a range of $0.06\text{--}0.07\text{gkg}^{-1}$ and the subsurface range from $0.06\text{--}0.11\text{gkg}^{-1}$.

Soil unit ARF2, recorded a range of $0.06\text{--}0.10\text{gkg}^{-1}$, with a mean value of 0.08gkg^{-1} . The highest (0.10gkg^{-1}) was found at the C horizon, while the lowest (0.06gkg^{-1}) took position at Ab horizon. The range for the surface horizon is $0.08\text{--}0.09\text{gkg}^{-1}$ and that of subsurface is $0.06\text{--}0.10\text{gkg}^{-1}$.

Soil unit ARF3 observed a range of $0.06\text{--}0.11\text{gkg}^{-1}$ and a mean value of 0.08gkg^{-1} TN. The highest range of 0.11gkg^{-1} occurred at the Bt horizon, while the lowest (0.06gkg^{-1}) was recorded at BC horizon. Surface horizons observed a range of $0.07\text{--}0.08\text{gkg}^{-1}$ and the subsurface horizon covered a range of $0.06\text{--}0.11\text{gkg}^{-1}$ TN. According to the TN rating by Esu [27, 28] $<0.1\text{gkg}^{-1}$ indicate low TN, $0.1\text{--}0.2\text{gkg}^{-1}$ medium, and $>0.2\text{gkg}^{-1}$ high. The mean TN values for ARF1, ARF2 and ARF3 were considered low.

Observably, TN distribution across the surface and subsurface horizons of the three mapping units showed irregular pattern of distribution with depth of profile. This could be attributed to leaching or vertical migration of clays. Accordingly, the result of low TN recorded in the study, aligns with previous studies conducted in the Sudan savannah agroecology of Yobe State, near Kebbi which reported TN with a range of $0.06\text{--}0.09\text{gkg}^{-1}$ as low, in different land uses, Abdullahi and Ibrahim [28]. Also, studies conducted in some part of Kebbi state by D'Hoore, [14] reported low TN.

Available Phosphorus (AP) for Soil unit ARF1 had a mean value of 14.03mgkg^{-1} at a range of $6.30\text{--}23.50\text{mgkg}^{-1}$. The highest range is 23.50mgkg^{-1} located at Ah horizon, while the lowest (6.30mgkg^{-1}) is seen at Btg horizon. The surface horizon recorded a range of $2.00\text{--}23.50\text{mgkg}^{-1}$ and the subsurface horizon recorded a range of $6.30\text{--}6.33\text{mgkg}^{-1}$.

Soil unit ARF2 showed up a mean AP value of 16.48mgkg^{-1} at a range of $9.90\text{--}25.50\text{mgkg}^{-1}$. The highest (25.50mgkg^{-1}) occurred at the Ap horizon, with the lowest (9.90mgkg^{-1}) at the Btg horizon. The surface horizon ranged from $2.00\text{--}25.50\text{mgkg}^{-1}$ while the subsurface horizons had range of $9.90\text{--}10.50\text{mgkg}^{-1}$.

Soil unit ARF3 surface and subsurface horizons recorded a range of $9.90\text{--}20.50\text{mgkg}^{-1}$ and a mean AP value of 14.93mgkg^{-1} , with the highest (20.50mgkg^{-1}) at the Ap horizon, while the lowest (9.00mgkg^{-1}) occurred at BC horizon. The range for surface horizons stood at $2.00\text{--}20.50\text{mgkg}^{-1}$ and that of subsurface horizons recorded from $9.00\text{--}10.50\text{mgkg}^{-1}$ AP. Ratings of AP by Esu, [27], is given as $<10\text{mgkg}^{-1}$ low, $10\text{--}20\text{mgkg}^{-1}$ moderate and $>20\text{mgkg}^{-1}$ high. The mean values of the three soil units therefore showed a moderate AP condition.

The trend of AP distribution in ARF1 was irregular with depth of profile, but ARF2 and ARF3 witnessed a regular trend with depth, which varied at the last subsurface horizons. This could be attributed to organic matter and fertilizer accumulations at the top and lower sub-soils. The slight increase in AP at the last subsurface horizon maybe tied to leaching and vertical clay migration, Abdullahi and Ibrahim [20]. While AP levels varied with particle size. Comparatively, the results of AP concentration obtained in the study, corroborate previous Sudan Savannah studies in Yobe state that reported low to moderate AP levels ($6.33\text{--}15.80\text{mgkg}^{-1}$) in different land uses, Abdullahi and Ibrahim [20].

Table 2, show that exchangeable bases took a similar trend in concentration (but slightly higher status in Mg), to that of surface soils. Exchangeable Mg dominated with high levels across the soil mapping units, followed by Na with moderate levels, while Ca and K reported low levels.

In soil unit ARF1, exchangeable Ca had a range of $0.00\text{--}0.10\text{cmolkg}^{-1}$ and a mean value of 0.05cmolkg^{-1} . The highest (0.01cmolkg^{-1}) occurred at the subsurface horizons of Btg and BCg, while the lowest (0.00cmolkg^{-1}) situates at the surface horizons Ap and Ah. The surface horizons recorded a total deficit in Ca concentration (0.00cmolkg^{-1}) while the subsurface has a fix range of 0.10cmolkg^{-1} . By the ratings of Esu, [27], $<2\text{cmolkg}^{-1}$ indicate low Ca $2\text{--}5\text{cmolkg}^{-1}$ medium and $>5\text{cmolkg}^{-1}$ high. The mean value of 0.05cmolkg^{-1} Ca in the soil unit was rated low.

Exchangeable Mg had a range of $0.35\text{--}1.50\text{cmolkg}^{-1}$ and a mean value of 1.09cmolkg^{-1} . The highest range of 1.50cmolkg^{-1} was seen at Btg and

BCg horizons, while the lowest (0.35 cmolkg^{-1}) was at the Ap horizon. Surface horizons range from $0.35\text{-}1.00 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$ Mg and subsurface horizons recorded a fix range of 1.50 cmolkg^{-1} . By Esu, [27] ratings ($<0.3 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$ Mg indicates low $0.3\text{-}1.0 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$ Medium and $>1.0 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$ high) The mean value of 1.09 cmolkg^{-1} Mg was considered high.

Exchangeable K in the soil unit stood at a range of $0.04\text{-}0.10 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$ with a mean value of 0.07 cmolkg^{-1} . The highest value of 0.10 cmolkg^{-1} situates at the BCg horizon and the lowest (0.04 cmolkg^{-1}) at Ap horizon. The range for the surface horizons is $0.04\text{-}0.05 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$, while that of subsurface horizons is from $0.07\text{-}0.10 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$. Ratings for K shows (that $<0.15 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$ signifies low, $0.15\text{-}0.3 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$ medium and $>0.3 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$ high). The mean value of 0.07 cmolkg^{-1} K indicates low concentration.

Exchangeable Na at a range of $0.13\text{-}0.44 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$ reported a mean value of 0.30 cmolkg^{-1} . The highest (0.44 cmolkg^{-1}) occurred at the BCg horizon and the lowest (0.13 cmolkg^{-1}) was found at the Ap horizon. Surface horizons range from $0.13\text{-}0.23 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$, while the subsurface horizons had a range of $0.40\text{-}0.44 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$. From the ratings of Na ($<0.1 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$ indicates low, $0.1\text{-}0.3 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$ moderate, and $>0.3 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$ high). The mean value for Na (0.30 cmolkg^{-1}) for the soil unit represents a moderate condition.

Soil unit ARF2 recorded a mean value for exchangeable Ca as 0.07 cmolkg^{-1} at a range of $0.00\text{-}0.10 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$. The highest range (0.10 cmolkg^{-1}) pitched at the Ap and Btg horizons. The lowest range of total deficit occurred at the horizon. Surface horizons range from $0.07\text{-}0.10 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$, while subsurface horizons range from $0.00\text{-}0.10 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$. The mean value Ca (0.07 cmolkg^{-1}) so recorded indicates low status.

Exchangeable Mg had a range of $0.38\text{-}1.55 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$, with a mean value of 1.23 cmolkg^{-1} . The highest value of 1.55 cmolkg^{-1} locates at the C horizon and the lowest occur at Ap horizon. Range for surface horizon is $0.38\text{-}1.50 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$, while that of subsurface horizons is $1.50\text{-}1.55 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$. The mean value 1.23 cmolkg^{-1} is rated high.

Exchangeable K for the soil unit recorded a range of $0.05\text{-}0.06 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$, with a mean value of

0.05 cmolkg^{-1} . The highest range of 0.06 cmolkg^{-1} occur at Btg horizon, while the lowest (0.05 cmolkg^{-1}) situates at Ap, AB and C horizons. The range for surface horizons was constant and subsurface varies from $0.05\text{-}0.06 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$. The mean value 0.05 cmolkg^{-1} for the soil unit is rated low

Exchangeable Na had a mean value of 0.20 cmolkg^{-1} at a range of $0.18\text{-}0.22 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$. Highest is 0.22 cmolkg^{-1} and occurred at the AB horizon, while the lowest (0.18 cmolkg^{-1}) situates at Btg horizon. Surface horizons range from $0.19\text{-}0.22 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$ and subsurface horizon had a range of $0.18\text{-}0.20 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$. The mean Na value of 0.20 cmolkg^{-1} is considered moderate.

Soil unit ARF3 had a range of Ca from $0.03\text{-}0.10 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$, with a mean value of 0.08 cmolkg^{-1} . The highest of 0.10 cmolkg^{-1} was found at Ap and Bt horizons, while the lowest (0.03 cmolkg^{-1}) occurred at the BC horizon. Surface horizons had a range of $0.07\text{-}0.10 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$ and subsurface range form $0.03\text{-}0.10 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$. The 0.08 cmolkg^{-1} mean value Ca is rated low.

Exchangeable Mg at the soil unit recorded a range of $1.00\text{-}1.50 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$ and a mean value of 1.30 cmolkg^{-1} . The highest range (1.50 cmolkg^{-1}) occurred at the AB and Bt horizons. The lowest (1.00 cmolkg^{-1}) locates at BC horizon. Surface horizons range from $1.20\text{-}1.50 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$, while subsurface horizons recorded a range of $1.00\text{-}1.50 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$. The mean value Mg of 1.30 cmolkg^{-1} for the soil unit represents high concentration.

Exchangeable K in this unit ranged from $0.04\text{-}0.05 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$, with a mean value of 0.04 cmolkg^{-1} . The highest (0.05 cmolkg^{-1}) was seen at the Ap horizon, while the lowest (0.04 cmolkg^{-1}) remained steady at AB, BC and Bt horizons. Surface horizons range from $0.04\text{-}0.05 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$ and the subsurface horizons remained fixed at 0.04 cmolkg^{-1} . The mean value K of 0.04 cmolkg^{-1} was rated low in the soil unit.

Exchangeable Na for the mapping unit recorded a range of $0.19\text{-}0.38 \text{ cmolkg}^{-1}$ and a mean value of 0.25 cmolkg^{-1} . The highest value of 0.38 cmolkg^{-1} occurred at the AB horizon, while the lowest (0.19 cmolkg^{-1}) situates at BC horizon. The range for the surface horizons strikes from 0.21-

0.38cmolkg⁻¹. The mean value of Na recorded in this unit is rated as moderate.

Observably, soil unit ARF1 showed a regular increase with depth of all the exchangeable bases throughout the profile.

ARF2 and ARF3 showed irregular pattern with depth for some of the basic cations.

Drawing from the results of both surface soils and subsurface soils, it could be observed that Ca and K were mostly impacted, hence the need to improve their status and availability. This can be achieved through the following measures; addition of organic matter – incorporate crop residues, manure or compost to increase CEC, apply balance fertilizer – use fertilizers containing Ca, Mg and K to replenish exchangeable bases, crop rotation and inter-cropping; rotate crops and inter-crop legumes to improve soil fertility and structure, conservation agriculture implement practices like mulching and minimum tillage to reduce soil erosion and improve soil health. These strategies can help enhance soil fertility and productivity in Sudan Savannah agorecology. CEC across the three soil units reflected a low status similar to the surface soils.

Soil unit ARF1 recorded a CEC range of 0.52-2.14cmolkg⁻¹, with a mean value 1.50cmolkg⁻¹. The highest (2.14cmolkg⁻¹) has its position at BCg horizon, while the lowest (0.52cmolkg⁻¹) situates at Ap horizon.

The range for the surface horizon is from 0.52-1.28cmolkg⁻¹ and that for subsurface proceeds form 2.07-2.14cmolkg⁻¹. FAO [1] and Esu, [28] rating, CEC <6cmolkg⁻¹ is low, 6-12 medium, and >12cmolkg⁻¹ high. The mean value of 1.50cmolkg⁻¹ CEC is rated low.

In ARF2 soil unit, CEC range stood at 0.72-1.84cmolkg⁻¹, with a mean value of 1.55cmolkg⁻¹. The highest (1.84cmolkg⁻¹) range is located at AB and Btg horizons, while the lowest value of 0.72cmolkg⁻¹ occur at the Ap horizon. Surface horizons range from 0.72-1.84cmolkg⁻¹ and subsurface horizons have a range of 1.80-1.84cmolkg⁻¹. The mean value (1.55cmolkg⁻¹) for the soil unit is considered low.

ARF3 soil unit have a CEC range of 1.26-1.99cmolkg⁻¹ and a mean value of 1.67cmolkg⁻¹. 1.99cmolkg⁻¹ is the highest and occurred at the AB horizon, while the lowest 1.26cmolkg⁻¹ is located at BC horizon. Surface horizons range from 1.56-1.99 cmolkg⁻¹ and the subsurface have range from 1.26-1.87cmolkg⁻¹. The mean CEC value (1.67cmolkg⁻¹) obtained in the mapping unit represents low status.

Across the mapping units, there is an observed increase in CEC with depth of the profiles. The low CEC reported in the entire study area could be a reflection of the pH range (4.4-5.1) of strongly acidic to moderately acidic condition, low organic matter content, prevalence of low activity clays as well as the granitic sand dominance amongst other factors, confirming studies by D'Hoore [14] and IUSS [13].

Table 3: Sodicty Evaluation

Sample Area	ESP (%)	SAR	ESP Rating	SAR Rating
Surface Soils	14.86	0.39	Slightly Sodic	Non-Sodic
Soil Unit ARF1	15.00	0.40	Slightly Sodic	Non-Sodic
Soil Unit ARF2	12.90	0.91	Slightly sodic	Non-Sodic
Soil Unit ARF3	14.97	0.15	Slightly sodic	Non-Sodic

KEY: ESP = Exchangeable Sodium Percentage; SAR = Sodium Adsorption Ratio

Both Exchangeable Sodium percentage (ESP) and sodium adsorption ratio (SAR) are used to measure Soil Sodicty. Assessment of sodicty based on ESP of the surface soils and mapping units of the study area revealed moderate (slightly sodic) conditions respectively.

The surface soils ESP 14.86%, ARF1 ESP 15.0%, ARF2 ESP 12.90% and ARF3 ESP 14.97% were rated moderate. This implies that the entire study area poses a sodium risk, indicating the likelihood of the soil to experience sodium related problems such as dispersion, leading to poor structure, reduced porosity and increased erosion risk, plant toxicity, reduced growth and crop yields, also

reduced water infiltration rates, making them pruned to water-logging and runoff. These soils therefore may not be suitable to a wide range of crops and management practices. Special management practices, such as application of gypsum, proper irrigation and drainage to reduce sodium levels and improve soil structure may be required. These can impact agricultural productivity, water use efficiency and overall soil health.

Based on SAR, sodicity assessment of the surface soils and the three mapping units, recorded a non-sodic condition. SAR for surface soil was 0.39, considered non-sodic (low level). ARF1 recorded 0.40 (non-sodic), ARF2 SAR was 0.91 (non-sodic) and ARF3 SAR value was 0.15 indicating low level and non-sodic too. Therefore, the SAR of the entire study area suggest a normal soil with low sodium risk, good soil structure and less management concern regarding sodium level, making it suitable for a wide range of crops and management practices. The low SAR also suggests a soil with favourable chemical properties for plant growth and agricultural use.

4.0 Conclusion

Assessment of soil chemical property is a necessary approach to enhancing agricultural production in Nigerian and Aliero in particular. Though expanding population and farming activities, has exerted pressure on available soil resources (near farms), leading to nutrient lost with low crop production and food supply chain. This scenario call for concern with rising demand for experimental data that would evolve sustainable management practice to protect the soil resource base. Therefore, soil chemical properties assessment and mapping serve as a valuable resource for food security and environmental sustainability in the study area.

5.0 Recommendations

- Low Moisture Content should be addressed through crops selection suitable to local condition and climate with irrigation system to contain dry spell.
- Fertilizer (balance fertilizers containing Ca, Mg and K) and organic amendments based on soil test results should be applied.
- Soil acidity (low pH) soil acidity should be addressed by liming. While Sodicity

should be addressed by application of gypsum, proper irrigation and drainage to reduce the exchangeable Na

6.0 Acknowledgment

We give all credibility and credence to God the creator for the knowledge and confidence he has bestowed on us to work as a team. We likewise thank every authors in this paper for their concise contributions in terms of intellectual materials and financial support to carryout the field and laboratory analysis, your effort is highly acknowledged. The works of the ad hoc or support field assistants is hereby appreciated. The department of Soil Science, faculty of Agriculture Abdullahi Fodiyo University of Science and Technology Aliero, Kebbi state Laboratory staff who never relented to ensuring timely result are ably recognized. We also recognized the services of our typist who has shown colossal resilience toward fast delivery and perfect work. The effort of those who contributed in one way or the other to the success of this research is hereby acknowledged and we say thank you all.

7.0 Conflict of Interest

Authors hereby declare that there is no conflict of interest whatsoever.

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